

ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF BEAUTY

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Abstract: This article contains various theories, views and teachings related to beauty. The concept of beauty is also considered a linguistic-mental concept related to the linguistic landscape and perception of the world. This article talks about the beauty of nature, female and male beauty, as well as the research on the concept of beauty described in world linguistics.

Keywords: Concept, notion, verbalize, conceptual analysis, lexeme, linguaculture, standard.

Introduction:

In world linguistics, the changes specific to the stages of development of the historical development of any language, the relationship between language and thought in a certain period are determined on the basis of the research of artistic texts that are the product of people's thinking and values. That's why linguistics today gives a wide place to the study of language materials from a cognitive aspect. In this direction, attention has been paid to the conceptual aspects of classical artistic texts based on national-ethnic, emotional-aesthetic principles. The analysis of the national-cultural values of a certain nation on the example of the leading concept in classical artistic texts - the vision of beauty and its assessment criteria is important in illuminating the development of national consciousness and artistic thinking. Conceptual analysis of classical works in world linguistics, the people reflected in them. The cognitive approach to the issues of determining spiritual values, determining the place of lexical units in concept formation led to clear solutions about the mental nature of language. The achievements in this direction allow to systematize the historical vocabulary within a separate concept based on the linguistic and cultural characteristics of the classical texts against the background of the national culture of the Turkic peoples.

In this regard, it is necessary to determine the verbalization of the concept of beauty in artistic texts through various means, the image possibilities specific to the period of the old Uzbek language, the poetic evaluation of beauty and the oriental standards within this concept, the detailed analysis of lexical-semantic processes in

artistic texts, and through this summarizing the characteristics of the important historical stage of the Uzbek language is one of the most urgent issues. During the years of Independence in Uzbek linguistics, a number of studies were carried out within the framework of anthropocentric and cognitive linguistics, conceptual problems, and attention to research devoted to the analysis of classical texts increased. After all, the history of the Uzbek language, which belongs to the big family of Turkic languages, is closely connected with its centuries-old past, its dreams, sorrows and victories¹.

Our ancestors spoke to the world through our mother tongue. They created great examples of culture, great scientific discoveries, and artistic masterpieces in this language. Therefore, researching the spiritual masterpieces embodied in these artistic treasures on a scientific basis of great importance in determining the spiritual and aesthetic views of the Turkic people, especially the Uzbek people, and the linguistic features of classical texts, a unity that manifests mentally in his mind, reflects the worldview, national-ethnic characteristics of the language's owners.

The principle of dividing the substantive structure of the concept of beauty into two groups - the thematic groups of nature and human beauty can be applied to Uzbek classical literature. Although Central Asian philosophers perceived beauty in the spirit of Islamic beliefs, they tried to emphasize that beauty is a complex spiritual process. According to them, the source of total beauty is the God, and the beauty in reality is a reflection of the beauty of God.

—Jamal

—purity,

Expressions such as "decoration" are compared to beauty in Sufism. The foundation of Sufism is the beauty of the heart and a high mind. Uzbek classic artistic texts contain images related to the beauty of nature. The image of spring has taken place in written literature, starting with Yusuf Khos Hajib:

Tug‘ardin esa keldi o‘ngdun eli Ajun etguka achi ushtmah, yo‘li

(The first spring breeze blew from the east, opening the way to paradise to decorate the universe).

The roots of the linguopoetic interpretation of male beauty in the Turkic people go back to the ancient monuments of the V-VII centuries. Commander, Khakan's close adviser Tonyuquq is not only a brave, brave, strict, steadfast and experienced general, but also a knowledgeable person of his time. The description of men also includes criteria of aesthetic evaluation comparable to legendary symbols such as prophet Yusuf, epos Rustam, Alpomish. The lexeme “Polvon”(strong man) applied to men of

¹ President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's speech at the ceremony dedicated to the thirtieth anniversary of the granting of the status of the State language to the Uzbek language // —The People's Speech, October 22, 2019

the male gender, as a linguo-cultural term, expresses the characteristic features of the Uzbek people: tall stature, broad shoulders, and strength.²

It should be noted that in classical literature, any beauty is associated with the image of a woman. It can be said that the concept of beauty arose mainly on the ground of love for “yor” (God in Sufi poetry), for a woman.

In the image space of the national-ethnic values of the Uzbek people, an oriental, Uzbek standard of female beauty was created, which was expressed in the linguopoetic features of the literature of each period. In Uzbek classical literature, the concept of beauty is verbalized mainly in the form of a woman, and an ideal standard of beauty is created by reflecting its linguistic expression against the background of strong expressive colors. The concept of beauty is a woman, love, nature, human belongs to the same conceptsphere with concepts like lexemes such as beauty, fascination, grace are the core of the concept; beautiful, graceful, handsome, charming, attractive, handsome, good-looking, flawless, perfect, clean, pure; surprising, pleasing, inspiring: units such as love, pleasure, longing, joy, pain, dream, lover form layers of periphery at different levels. In recent years, much attention has been paid to the cognitive aspect of language units, and in the research conducted in this field, it has been scientifically substantiated that existing language units appear as a result of human re-understanding.³

J. Lakoff and M. Johnson show that two cognitive fields, namely the source field and the target field are involved in the emergence of metaphorical derived meaning. The source field is a collection of specific knowledge in the perception of existence through human experience. And the target area is a knowledge that is relatively poorly clarified and inevitable to be determined.⁴ In the following example from Lutfiy's verse, the beauty of the face, hair and cheeks is verbalized based on symbols (colors) transferred from one area to another area:

Ul orazu ruxsor ila zulfi, engi lola,

Oydinda yetur gul uza bir hindu uzola (Ul orazu ruxsor ila).

(She is the youngest of the tulips. In the moon there are four flowers and one Hindu flower (Ul orazu rukhsor ila)).

Literature analysis and methodology:

In linguistics, the attention to the problem of the national view of the world, the expression of value in language, aesthetic value, concepts and interpretations devoted to their theoretical research has begun to increase. These directions are W. von

² Kadirova B.R. Belgi bildiruvchi leksemalarning lingvokulturologik xususiyatlari: Filol. fan. b-cha fals. d-ri (PhD) diss. avtoref. – Toshkent, 2019. – B.15.

³ Rahmatova Mehriniso Mo’sinova “Ingliz ,o’zbek ,tojik milliy madaniyatida “Go’zallik” konseptining lisoniy xususiyatlari” dissertatsiya Buxoro 2019

⁴ Yuldashev A.G.Ko’chma ma’noli so’zlarda kognitiv mexanizmlarning o’rni // —O’zbekistonda xorijiy tillar ilmiy-metodik elektron jurnal journal.fledu.uz № 3/2019. – B.60.

Humboldt, R.W. Langaker, Dj.P. Lakoff, N.D. Arutyunova, V.I. Karasik, Ye.S. Kubryakova, Yu.V. Mesheryakova, I.O. Okuneva, Yu.V. Klinsova, T.N. Fedotova, L.I. Zakharova, A.A. Potebnya, A.G. Vezhbiskaya, Yu.D. Apresyan, I.F. Sternin, Yu.S. Stepanov, V.A. Maslova, K.V. Sboroshenko, N.F. Alefirenko, A.T. Khrolenko, I.O. Okuneva, R.N. Popova, E.J. Munin, O.A. Kornilov; in Tajik linguistics, it is observed in the studies of A.V. Arzumanov, D.M. Iskandarova, N.I. Karimova, R.R. Radjabova, N.K. Boymatova. In the researches of A.A. Abduazizov, D.U. Ashurova, Sh.S. Safarov, M.R. Galiyeva, A.E. Mamatov, M.N. Kholbekov, M.I. Rasulova, O'.Q. Yusupov, A.A. Kambarov, S.R. Akbarova, Q.N. Nazarov, M.M. Rakhmatova, N.R. Umarova in Uzbek linguistics studied to a certain extent. In researches related to the concept of beauty, attention was paid to national-ethnic and linguistic-cultural characteristics.

In particular, the Russian linguist K. V. Sboroshenko explained the concept of beauty in the poems of Russian and Italian poets of the 20th century based on a metaphorical analysis.⁵ Yu.V. Mesheryakova's dissertation was devoted to comparative and linguistic-cultural analyzes of the concept of beauty in English and Russian languages⁶, while A.V. Molchanova's research analyzed the specific aspects of the concept of beauty in the works of B. Pasternak⁷. Ye.A. Cherkashina studied the expression of beauty in the Russian language on the basis of lexicographic materials and phraseological units⁸. The concept of "beauty" in Russian and English was studied in the candidate's thesis of I. O. Okuneva in a comparative aspect⁹. In N.K. Boymatova's candidacy thesis¹⁰, the representation of the concept of beauty in Tajik and English languages was compared. M.M. Rakhmatova researched the linguistic features of the concept of beauty in Uzbek, English and Tajik languages.¹¹ T. Yandashova combined the expression and linguopoetics of this concept based on the comparative analysis of the Uzbek and English languages¹². Until now, most of the works devoted to the study of the concept of beauty have been carried out within the

⁵ Сборошенко К.В. Метафорическая репрезентация концепта —красота|| в современной поэзии (на материале стихотворений русских и итальянских поэтов XX века): Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Челябинск, 2009.

⁶ Мешеерякова Ю.В. Концепт —Красота в английской и русской лингвокультурах: Автореф. дисс. канд. филол. наук. – Волгоград, 2004.

⁷ Молчанова А.В. Художественная концепция красоты в творчестве Б.Пастернака: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Казан, 2010.

⁸ Черкашина Е.А. Концепт —Красота в русском языке // Вестник ТГПИ, УДК 81 ББК 81.43

⁹ Окунева И.О. Концепт —Красота в русском и английском языках: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Москва, 2009

¹⁰Бойматова Н.К. Семантическое поле концепта —Красота в таджикской и английской лингвокультурах: Автореф. дисс. канд. филол. наук. – Душанбе, 2019.

¹¹ Rahmatova M.M. Ingliz, o'zbek va tojik milliy madaniyatida —Go'zallik konseptining lisoniy xususiyatlari: Fals. d-ri(PhD) ... diss. avtoref. – Buxoro, 2019.

¹²Yandashova T.O'zbek va ingliz tillarida —go'zallik konseptining ifodalanishi va lingvopoetikasi: Fals. d-ri (PhD) diss. avtoref. – Toshkent, 2021.

framework of more than one language, in a comparative aspect, and in this work, the issue of the expression of the concept of beauty in classical artistic texts is being researched.

Discussion and results:

The purpose of the research is to reveal the verbalization of the concept of beauty in Uzbek classic artistic texts and the units in interaction with this concept. The tasks of the research: to determine the linguistic and cultural characteristics of oriental beauty, the verbalization of the concept of beauty in the old Uzbek literary language, as well as to study the axiological characteristics of beauty in classical texts, the general and differential aspects of the concepts of beauty specific to the East and the West defining, clarifying the fact that the concept of oriental beauty is mainly related to the image of a woman and its verbalization within the concepts of love, defining the level of national-ethnic and emotional-aesthetic evaluation embodied in poetic texts: the leading role of linguistic and cultural features in the linguistic conceptualization of the world justification of behavior; lexical-semantic analysis of the structure of lexemes representing beauty, determination of the composition of cognitive mechanisms verbalizing the concept of beauty, substantiation of the national-cultural characteristics of the image of beauty created by means of stable units.

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